

A study in Complexity

By Kyriakos Sourmelis

“The art of programming is the art of organizing complexity, of mastering multitude and avoiding its bastard chaos as effectively as possible”.

E. W. Dijkstra

The great Edsger Wybe Dijkstra was a computer programmer, systems engineer, computer scientist, systems scientist, and a pioneer in computing science. He is a towering figure in the world of computers and has offered a lot in the field of this study. The above quote by him shows how difficult it is conceiving a program written in such a way that is essentially very simple, despite the monstrous tasks it undertakes. In fact, it is so difficult, for him is an art form. But what does Dijkstra mean when he mentions the bastard chaos of complexity?

First, some basic concepts need to be established. In logic, mathematics, and computer science, a solution is defined based on its effectiveness i.e., produces a solution or not. An effective method for solving a problem from a specific class is called definition, mechanical method, or a procedure. For a method to be called effective for a class of problems, it needs to satisfy several criteria. These include the finite, countable, and exact number of clear instructions, the process must always terminate after a finite number of steps, and it must always produce a correct answer to the problem at hand. These clear instructions can be performed by a human without any aids except writing materials, and they need to be followed rigorously. There are cases in which the problem, as a solution, has no solution. This means that the process or method has been applied to a problem from outside its own class.

The method mentioned above that needs to be applied step-by-step to obtain a solution, is called an algorithm. The word algorithm is derived from the 9th-century Persian mathematician Muḥammad ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī. His last name is Latinized as *Algoritmi*. A partial formalization of what would later become the modern concept of algorithm, began with attempts to solve the Entscheidungsproblem (decision problem) posed by David Hilbert in 1928. Later formalizations were framed as attempts to define "effective calculability" or "effective method". Those formalizations included the Gödel–Herbrand–Kleene recursive functions of 1930, 1934 and 1935, Alonzo Church's lambda calculus of 1936, Emil Post's Formulation 1 of 1936, and Alan Turing's Turing machines of 1936–37 and 1939.

The concept of algorithm has been around for centuries. Arithmetic algorithms, such as a division algorithm, was used by ancient Babylonian mathematicians c. 2500 BC and Egyptian mathematicians c. 1550 BC. Greek mathematicians later used algorithms in the sieve of Eratosthenes for finding prime numbers, and the Euclidean algorithm for finding the greatest common divisor of two numbers. Arabic mathematicians such as Al-Kindi in the 9th century used cryptographic algorithms for codebreaking, based on frequency analysis.

One has to distinguish between algorithms that use the random input so that they always terminate with the correct answer, but where the expected running time is finite (Las Vegas algorithms; for example, Quicksort), and algorithms which have a chance of producing an incorrect result (Monte Carlo algorithms; for example the Monte Carlo algorithm for the MFAS problem) or fail to produce a result either by signaling a failure or failing to terminate. In some cases, probabilistic algorithms are the only practical means of solving a problem.

Another type of algorithm in use today is the randomized algorithm. The randomized algorithm employs a degree of randomness as part of its logic. The algorithm typically uses uniformly random bits as an auxiliary input to guide its behavior, in the hope of achieving good performance in the "average case" over all possible choices of random bits. Formally, the algorithm's performance will be a random variable determined by the random bits; thus, either the running time, or the output, or both are random variables. In common practice, randomized algorithms are approximated using a pseudorandom number generator in place of a true source of random bits; such an implementation may deviate from the expected theoretical behavior.

An algorithm can be expressed within a finite amount of space and time, and in a well-defined formal language for calculating a function. Starting from an initial state and initial input (either empty or with an input other than zero or empty), the instructions describe a computation that, when executed, proceeds through a finite number of well-defined successive states, eventually producing "output" and terminating at a final ending state. The transition from one state to the next is not necessarily deterministic; some algorithms, known as randomized algorithms, incorporate random input.

An algorithm is called efficient when the function's values are small or grow slowly compared to a growth in the size of the input. Different inputs of the same length may cause the algorithm to have different behavior. When not otherwise specified, the function describing the performance of an algorithm is usually an upper bound, determined from the worst-case inputs to the algorithm. The image below shows the first published algorithm from "note G" from Ada Lovelace's diagram:

Diagram for the computation by the Engine of the Numbers of Bernoulli. See Note G. (page 722 et seq.)

Number of Operations.	Name of Operation.	Variable acted upon.	Variables receiving results.	Indication of change in the value on any Variable.	Statement of Results.	Data.												Working Variables.												Result Variables.																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																														
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complexity from computability theory: the latter theory asks what kind of problems can, in principle, be solved algorithmically.

Without the existence of an algorithm, computability cannot exist. There are a lot of models within the world of computability, but the most widely studied ones are the Turing-computable, μ -recursive functions, and the lambda calculus, all of which have the same computational power. Anything weaker in computability terms when it comes to the Turing machine is studied in automata theory, while anything stronger is studied in the fields of hypercomputation.

There are two types of problems that deal with the task of exploring computability. These problems are divided in decision problems where a fixed set S of strings or natural numbers are taken from a larger set U and given an element u of U at a particular instance, we need to find whether u is in S ; and in function problems where a function f from a set U points to a set V , i.e., $f(u) \in V$. There are lesser problems that deal with complexity ((lesser in the term of not being key tasks) and they include search problems and optimization problems.

The main goal of computability theory is to determine which problems can be solved with each of the available models of computation. These models of computation are always equivalent to a Turing machine which means that they take the form of an abstract machine that is meant to perform the task at hand. According to the Church – Turing thesis, these models include the Lambda calculus, combinatory logic, μ -recursive functions, string rewriting systems, register machine, Turing machine, multitape Turing machine, deterministic finite automaton (DFA), nondeterministic finite automaton (NFA), and pushdown automaton.

Let us look at the models proposed here for computability theory. The first one is the Lambda calculus. Lambda calculus or λ -calculus is a formal system in mathematical logic for expressing computation based on function abstraction and application using variable binding and substitution. It can be used to simulate any Turing machine. It was introduced by the mathematician and logician Alonzo Church in the 1930s as a companion to his Church – Turing thesis he wrote with Alan Turing. The thesis states that a function on the natural numbers can only be calculated if and only if it is computable by a Turing machine, and despite its universal acceptance, it cannot be formally proven. Lambda calculus, terms are built using only the following rules:

Syntax	Name	Description
X	Variable	A character or string representing a parameter or mathematical / logical value.
$(\lambda X.M)$	Abstraction	Function definition (M is a lambda term). The variable x becomes bound in the expression.
$(M N)$	Application	Applying a function to an argument. M and N are lambda terms.

Due to the nature of the theorem, a term in the lambda calculus has at most one normal form, justifying reference to "the normal form" of a given normalizable term. For some applications, terms for logical and mathematical constants and operations may be included, as well as applying several reduction methods. These reduction methods are put in place to reduce the initial expression. There are three (3) available types of reduction; the α -conversion (changes the bound variables), the β -reduction

(applies functions to the respective arguments) and the η -reduction (captures a notion of extensionality, adding or dropping the abstraction of a function), as shown in the table below.

Operation	Name	Description
$(\lambda x.M[x]) \rightarrow (\lambda y.M[y])$	α -conversion	Renaming the bound variables in the expression. Used to avoid name collisions.
$((\lambda x.M) E) \rightarrow (M[x := E])$	β -reduction	Replacing the bound variables with the argument expression in the body of the abstraction.
$\lambda x.(f x) \rightarrow f=(\lambda x(f x))$	η -reduction	Allows for the conversion between lambda $\lambda x.(f x)$ and f whenever x is not a free variable in f . This is called removing the abstraction.

The reduction in terms in the lambda calculus can also be done using the de Bruijn index. The de Bruijn index is a tool invented by the Dutch mathematician Nicolaas Govert de Bruijn for representing terms of lambda calculus without naming the bound variables. Terms written using these indices are invariant with respect to α -conversion, so the check for α -equivalence is the same as that for syntactic equality. Each de Bruijn index is a natural number that represents an occurrence of a variable in a λ -term and denotes the number of binders that are in scope between that occurrence and its corresponding binder. The following are some examples:

- ❖ The term $\lambda x. \lambda y. x$, sometimes called the K combinator, is written as $\lambda \lambda 2$ with De Bruijn indices. The binder for the occurrence x is the second λ in scope.
- ❖ The term $\lambda x. \lambda y. \lambda z. x z (y z)$ (the S combinator), with de Bruijn indices, is $\lambda \lambda \lambda 3 1 (2 1)$.
- ❖ The term $\lambda z. (\lambda y. y (\lambda x. x)) (\lambda x. z x)$ is $\lambda (\lambda 1 (\lambda 1)) (\lambda 2 1)$. See the following illustration, where the binders are coloured and the references are shown with arrows.

More precisely, if there are two distinct reductions or sequences of reductions that can be applied to the same term, then there exists a term that is reachable from both results, by applying (possibly empty) sequences of additional reductions. The theorem was proved in 1936 by Alonzo Church and J. Barkley Rosser, after whom it is named. This theorem, (it is known as the Church – Rosser theorem) states that, when applying reduction rules to terms in some typed variants of the lambda calculus, the ordering in which the reductions are chosen does not make a difference to the eventual result. The theorem is symbolized by the diagram shown on the right.

According to it, if term a can be reduced to both b and c , then there must be a further term d to which both b and c can be reduced to. The theorem also states that the reduction rules of the lambda calculus are confluent. As a result of this, a term in the lambda calculus has at most one normal form, thus justifying its reference to "the normal form" of a given normalizable term.

The next thing to look at is the combinatory logic. Combinatory logic is a notation introduced to eliminate the need for any quantifiable variables in mathematical logic. This notation is a variant of the lambda calculus shown above and it is used to

replace functional abstraction by a limited set of combinators (primitive functions without free variables). This ability of the combinatory logic has given the possibility to model non-strict functional programming languages and hardware. A great example can be seen in the use of the programming language Unlambda which has only two primitive (S and K) and they are augmented with character input and output.

The μ -recursive function, or general recursive function, is the model of computability that can compute natural numbers from natural numbers in an intuitive way. This means that it can predict and represent the outputs and design of all functions that can be computed by Turing machines. The way this notation works is that it takes an array or a tuple of natural numbers and returns a single natural number. The capacity of the recursive function can be split to partial recursive functions and total recursive functions. The exact mathematical equations and representation of said functions are beyond the scope of this study.

String rewriting systems (SRS), also known as semi-Thue systems, are used to write over strings from data given from a finite alphabet and they are also a reduction system, like the rest of the notions in computability. They are mainly used for propositional logic problems as well as generating fractals, and are, of course, Turing complete. Given a binary relation R between fixed strings over the alphabet denoted by $s \rightarrow t$, an SRS extends the rewriting relation to all strings in which the left- and right-hand side of the rules appear as substrings. This is interpreted as $usv \rightarrow utv$, where u , s , v , and t are strings. The notation here is very useful in computability as it can determine given a string input whether its computability can be reduced. SRS was used to help determine the solution to the halting problem (given a command, will a program ever terminate) back in the 1950's. It also helped Noam Chomsky establish the unrestricted grammar class for automata, where there is no restriction between the two sets (starting and ending) except for the starter set not to be empty. The classes also led Chomsky, along with Schützenberger, to establish the Chomsky – Schützenberger hierarchy in the development of formal grammars.

By Σ, retouched by Wugapodes - File:Noam_Chomsky_portrait_2017.jpg, CC BY-SA 4.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=85616571>

A register machine is, in its principle, a Turing machine. It basically takes a generic class of abstract machines and turns it into an equivalent Turing machine, although the resulting model's computational speed is heavily dependent on the initial machine's specifics. In turn, a Turing machine is a

mathematical model of computation that defines an abstract machine, which manipulates symbols on a strip of tape according to a table of rules. The Turing machine will read the input from a tape using a head, and then determine the output after performing a series of calculations. Despite the model's simplicity, given any computer algorithm, a Turing machine capable of simulating that algorithm's logic can be constructed. Turing machines proved the existence of fundamental limitations on the power of mechanical computation. It is also worth noting that modern day computers are based on Turing machines, albeit modern computers utilize random access memory, unlike the Turing machine. A multi-tape Turing machine behaves the same way as a Turing machine with the only difference that it has multiple inputs, i.e., reads from multiple tapes simultaneously using more than one heads.

All the above methods are based deep in their core to machines that can extract results using minimum information and they have predetermined states. This kind of machines are called Deterministic State Automata (DSA), Finite State Automata (FSA) or Deterministic Turing Machines (DTM). These machines operate on the basis that they accept a series of characters (or words) from a given alphabet and using reduction and abstract mathematical models, through finite states, they will determine an output. The output, despite going through the mathematical, or succumbing to reduction, models, depends entirely on the input the machine is given. The DSA is described as such when each of its transitions is uniquely determined by its source state and input symbol and requires an input symbol for each state transition. Their strict nature does not allow alterations to the nature of the DSA. However, there are machines that do not follow these guidelines. This kind of machines are called Non-deterministic Finite Automata (NFA), or Non-deterministic Turing Machines (NTM). Although it recognizes regular languages, the NFA will accept and consume an input and with each one of the symbols it consumes, it will transit to a new applicable state that is arbitrarily chosen.

By Vectorization: OmenBreeze - Own work based on: Difference between deterministic and Nondeterministic.png by Eleschinski2000, CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=84727658>

With each symbol, the NFA will check how many possible states exist and it will clone itself the appropriate number of times to follow each lead. If there are no applicable states, then the copy (or in case the original does not have a choice) will die. At the end of the consumption, if there are any copies in any of the states then the input is accepted. In any different case, the input will be rejected. Despite their differences, their similarities allow for an NFA to be turned into a DSA. This can be done with the usage of a powerset construction, which determines all the available states of the NFA with every input and then constructs the DSA using the results. In the rare of cases that the input of an NFA is a stack rather than a string of words, the automaton is now called a pushdown automaton. A pushdown automaton is more capable than a DSA but less capable than a Turing machine. Its usage lies in the processing of deterministic context free languages and that it can manipulate the elements as they lay in the stack, allowing the values of the stack to be smaller stacks in their own turn, called sub stacks.

A very good example in the usage of computability reduction is the primitive computer programming language P'' (p double prime) and it was designed to describe a family of Turing machines. It has also inspired an esoteric programming language called Brainfuck, which is a simplified version of P'' while they differ in the input and output methods.

It is worth noting here that there are two other models of computation besides the aforementioned. One of them, is the use of parallel processing by splitting computation on several processors that work simultaneously. There are two ways in which this model of computation works; the parallel computing where the data transmission is very fast, and the distributed computing where the data transmission is done over the network which makes it slower. The operation of parallel processing is based on the fact that a large program can be divided into smaller ones with a smaller execution time and the execution of said small problems takes place simultaneously. Once the smaller problems have been resolved, their solutions are combined and present the solution to the greater problem. Parallel processing is used in four different forms today; at bit-level (where the processor word size is increased resulting in less instructions the processor has to execute), at instruction level (where either at hardware level or software level, several instructions can be executed at the same time; here it should be noted that this is not concurrency, it is a different implementation), at data level (where data is distributed across different nodes utilizing multiple processors and it is analysed and processed on each one of them) and finally, at task level (where tasks are distributed across multiple processors for concurrent execution; the difference between this and data parallelism is that in the case of data the same task is run on multiple processors while for task, each processor is assigned the same task and no other processor executes said task). Parallel computing has gained many followers in recent years due to the power consumption required when undertaking large tasks and has led to multi-core processors in PCs which are more efficient while at the same time consuming less energy, thus generating much less heat.

An AMD Athlon X2 6400+ dual-core processor, by Babylonfive David W. Smith - Own work, CC BY 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=4027636>

Despite its popularity, parallel processing has a limitation in the execution of multi-threaded programming. This limitation is known as Amdahl's law or Amdahl's argument. Amdahl's law gives us the theoretical upper bound and theoretical speedup in latency of the execution of a task when the workload is fixed if the system's resources are improved. It is described by the following equation:

$$S_{\text{latency}}(s) = \frac{1}{(1 - p) + \frac{p}{s}}$$

where S_{latency} is the theoretical speedup of execution of the whole task, s is the number of threads the portion of the program that can be parallelized is split across, and p is the percentage of the workload that can be parallelized. If we analyse the above equation, we can see that the speedup of the program that can occur due to parallelization is increased by improving resources, but it will always be limited by the part that cannot be parallelized (serial part of the program).

$$S_{\text{latency}}(s) \leq \frac{1}{1-p}$$

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} S_{\text{latency}}(s) = \frac{1}{1-p}$$

The chart below shows the theoretical speedup of the latency of the execution of a program against the number of processors executing it, while keeping in mind that the speedup is limited by the serial part of the program that cannot be parallelized.

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The other model of computation that is gaining ground as we move forward is quantum computing. This is actually a really interesting one as it involves quantum computers. Quantum computers are the result of combining quantum physics principles, higher level mathematics and computer science. In order to understand why a quantum computer is called that, a few terms should be defined first. The quantum computer utilizes two phenomena to perform computations, superposition, and entanglement. Quantum superposition is the principle that asserts that two or more quantum states can be added together, or superposed, resulting in another valid quantum state. Vice-versa, a quantum state can be represented as the sum of two or more other distinct states. The superposition is something that we are familiar with from classical physics, when two or more waves interact and create a new wave. Quantum entanglement on the other hand, is the phenomenon that occurs when a group of two or more particles is generated, interact, or share spatial proximity in such a way that we cannot describe the quantum state of each particle independently, unless we describe the state of the other particles involved as well. Both principles can be seen when viewing the Schrödinger's Cat theoretical experiment, where a cat is in a sealed box with a radioactive material that has a 50% chance of decaying thus triggering a poison that would kill the cat. Without opening the box, we cannot say whether the cat is alive or not, so we assume that it is both alive and dead at the same time. This is resolved by opening the box and the observation collapses the superposition in one of the two states, alive or dead. It is worth noting that during the explanation of this experiment, Schrödinger is the one who coined the term quantum entanglement.

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How is this used in computers though? In the case of superposition, computer scientists created the quantum bit, or qubit. This is bit that exists in quantum superposition, where it can host both values 0 and 1 at the same time $|0\rangle + |1\rangle$ (this is the representation of the qubit in bra-ket or Dirac notation), whereas the normal bit can be either 0 or 1 at a time. In the case of quantum entanglement, the description of the qubit cannot take place unless we involve the current state of the machine as well as the state of the rest of the qubits. This shows that we cannot derive the value a qubit has unless we know the values for the rest of them. As an example, consider a system of n components, a complete description of its state in classical physics requires only n bits, whereas in quantum physics it requires 2^n complex numbers. A lot of companies deal with quantum computers nowadays such as IBM, Google and Nasa, Atom computing, Xanadu, D-Wave and Azure computing, with Google claiming that their computer executed a computation that would have taken ordinary supercomputers 10,000 years to perform, in 200 seconds. Just to have a perspective on how fast a quantum computer works, a traditional 4-bit computer register can hold any one of 16 possible numbers at a time. In contrast, a 4-qubit computer register can hold 16 different numbers simultaneously. In theory, a quantum computer can therefore operate on a great many values in parallel, so that a 30-qubit quantum computer would be comparable to a digital computer capable of performing 10 trillion floating-point operations per second (TFLOPS) — comparable to the speed of the fastest supercomputers today. This means that a quantum computer can complete a mathematical calculation that is demonstrably beyond the reach of even the most powerful supercomputer. It also means that it can solve problems that up until now were considered unsolvable or very difficult and time consuming, such as integer factorization (which is the basis for the RSA encryption algorithm) very fast.

The analysis of the algorithm on the other hand is the process of finding the computational complexity of algorithms (amount of time, storage, or other resources needed to execute them). The term "analysis of algorithms" was created by Donald Knuth. Algorithm analysis is an important part of the broader computational complexity theory, which provides theoretical estimates for the resources needed by any algorithm which solves a given computational problem. In this case, it is common to guess the algorithm's complexity in the asymptotic sense. Big O notation, Big-omega notation and Big-theta notation are used for this purpose. For example, binary search is said to run in a finite number of steps related to the logarithm of the length of the sorted list being searched, or $O(\log(n))$. Usually, asymptotic estimates are used because different implementations of the same algorithm may differ in efficiency. But the efficiencies of any two "reasonable" implementations of a given algorithm are related by a constant multiplicative factor called a hidden constant.

On the other hand, not asymptotic measures of efficiency can sometimes be computed but they usually require certain assumptions concerning this specific implementation of the algorithm, called model of computation. A model of computation may be defined in terms of an abstract computer, as we saw earlier, and/or by postulating that certain operations are executed in unit time. For instance, if the sorted list to which we apply binary search has n elements, and we can guarantee that each lookup of an element in the list can be done in unit time, then at most $\log(2n + 1)$ time units are needed to return an answer.

Computational complexity theory focuses on classifying computational problems according to their inherent difficulty and relating these classes to each other. A computational problem is a task solved by a computer by mechanical application of certain mathematical steps, such as an algorithm. The number of steps and resources need to be taken to resolve a problem (if the solution can be reached in a finite amount of time) has created categories based on difficulty of achieving a solution. A problem is considered as inherently difficult if its solution requires significant resources, whatever the algorithm used. The theory formalizes this intuition, by introducing mathematical models of computation to study these problems and quantifying their computational complexity, i.e., the amount of resources needed to solve them, time, and space complexity. Other measures of complexity are also used, such as the amount of communication (used in communication complexity), the number of gates in a circuit (used in circuit complexity) and the number of processors (used in parallel computing). One of the roles of computational complexity theory is to determine the practical limits on what computers can and cannot do. These problems are divided into two main categories: P and NP problems. P problems are problems that can provide a solution in polynomial time, while NP are problems that can be solved by a restricted class of brute force search algorithms and the solution can be used to simulate any other problem with a similar algorithm. The P versus NP problem (which states whether every problem whose solution can be quickly verified can also be solved quickly), one of the seven Millennium Prize Problems, is dedicated to the field of computational complexity. With the main terminology, the, somewhat, brief history lesson, and the grounds laid out, a detailed analysis of complexity follows.

Complexity is mainly divided into two large parts: unorganized and organized complexity. The unorganized complexity is because the parts that are supposed to be taken into consideration for determining the complexity of task, are mostly random. A good example of this would be a complex system that represents the Earth's global climate, or the human brain. In these systems, the complexity cannot be inferred easily or directly due to the many factors that contribute to its stabilization and creation. Usually, this kind of systems fall under the Chaos Theory section, which is a fascinating aspect of Physics. Organized complexity on the other hand is when the parts are not random at all, they are correlated, and they have interactions between them. Organized complexity can be represented in code and can produce results without any outside help. An example here would be the neighbourhood of a city, the people that live there and their behavioural patterns, as this constitutes a more predictable model with input data that is correlated to each data set.

When it comes to complexity in computer science, one of the things that come up is computational complexity. The computational complexity of an algorithm is the amount of resources needed to run the algorithm and produce a result. With each algorithm, the amount of resources required to run it, varies massively. This leads us to take into consideration two aspects of the computational complexity. These are time complexity and space complexity. For the record here, the complexity that is referred here, includes properties of a piece of software that affect internal interactions. This is not complicated, it is complex (albeit in this case is both). Complicated is something that is difficult to understand but with time and effort it will become understandable. Complex on the other hand is defined as the interactions between entities, and as the number of entities increase, the interactions between them increase exponentially, reaching a point where it would be impossible to know and understand all of them. It should also be noted here that when the subject is complexity, it is referring to the average case of complexity. The best-case complexity is not something that should be taken into consideration, as this is rarely the case for the problems at hand. Complexity also has a lower and upper bound, as it will show

The results shown in the graph above, the algorithmic time complexity, depending on the value that it returns, $T(n)$, can divide the algorithms into different classifications. These classifications are:

- The linear time $O(n)$, where the value of the time complexity increases linearly as the input increases.
- The polynomial time $O(n^a)$, where $a > 1$, where the algorithm takes polynomial time to be executed. This is where the P problems that were shown earlier occur from; these problems have a solution that take polynomial time to be executed and produce a result.
- The constant time $O(1)$, where the value of the complexity of the algorithm does not depend on the size of the input
- The logarithmic time $O(\log n)$. This type of algorithmic time is found when traversing binary trees or when using binary search. As a side note here, the base of the algorithm does not matter be that base 10, 8, or any other base, as the bases of a logarithm are related by a constant multiplier which does not mean anything to the time complexity notation.
- The polylogarithmic time $O((\log n)^k)$, where $k > 1$. Polylogarithmic time algorithms occur when multiplying multiple matrices on parallel random-access machines (these are abstract machines that have a shared memory) and to determine whether a given graph can be drawn in a plane without edge intersections (planarity of a graph).
- The sublinear time $o(n)$ (yes, that is a lower-case n ; it is not a typo). Sublinear time algorithms are any of the algorithms previously defined that can run on parallel machines at the same time (i.e. parallel processing)
- The quasilinear time $O(n \log^k n)$ where k is a positive constant. It is worth noting that since this is the time complexity for the quasilinear time, it could be easily defined through the big notation O as $O(n^{1+\epsilon})$ for every constant $\epsilon > 0$, and thus run faster than any polynomial time algorithm whose time bound includes a term n^c for any $c > 1$. Notable examples of this algorithmic time are the Quicksort algorithm, the Heapsort, and the Fast Fourier Transformations.
- The sub-quadratic time $o(n^2)$. This type of algorithms includes the insertion sort or the shell sort and it is worth noting that due to that there is no general purpose sort that runs in linear time, however, it is possible to alter the time from quadratic to sub-quadratic thus showcasing an edge over the time of execution.

There are a few more classifications in the algorithmic time processes that are worth a special mention as they need to be explained further and analysed in depth. Starting off with the polynomial time, that is mentioned above, where its running time is upper bounded by a polynomial expression in the size of the input for the algorithm. In case the input to the algorithm with a polynomial time is integer, then the complexity can also be divided into strong and weak polynomial time complexity. For an algorithm to be qualified as having a strong polynomial time complexity, it must adhere to the two following rules:

1. The number of operations in the arithmetic model of computation must be bounded by a polynomial in the number of integers in the input instance; and
2. The space used by the algorithm is bounded by a polynomial in the size of the input.

In case the algorithm does not adhere to the rules, but is still resolved in polynomial time, then it is said to be of weak polynomial time complexity. The most common example of weak polynomial time complexity is linear programming. The polynomial classification can also be distinguished into further sub-classes in computational complexity theory.

P	Class of decision problems that can be solved on a deterministic Turing machine in polynomial time
NP	Class of decision problems that can be solved on a non-deterministic Turing machine in polynomial time
ZPP	Class of decision problems that can be solved with zero error on a probabilistic Turing machine in polynomial time
RP	Class of decision problems that can be solved with 1-sided error on a probabilistic Turing machine in polynomial time.
BPP	Class of decision problems that can be solved with 2-sided error on a probabilistic Turing machine in polynomial time
BQP	Class of decision problems that can be solved with 2-sided error on a quantum Turing machine in polynomial time

Table 3

In class P, all decision problems can be solved in polynomial time. For a language to belong in this class, the Turing machine that is handling it should give a solution in polynomial time, for all the letters in the specific language the output should be 1 and for all the letters not belonging to the language the output should be 0. A great example of a problem belonging to this category is the finding of the greatest common denominator, as well as finding out if a number is prime or not. Cobham's thesis was used for a time and asserts that all computational problems can be feasibly computed on a computational device, only if they can be computed in polynomial time (thus referring to problems belonging to the P class). This, however, is not used today as it is shown going forward, many problems have risen that will not fall in this category, either by having no solution at all, or being computed in a polynomial time only in a quantum computer.

In NP, all decision problems can be solved in polynomial time with the use of a non-deterministic Turing machine. This is based on the fact that the correct answer can be proven in polynomial time. For a language to belong in this category, we theorise of two polynomials x and y with the usage of a non-deterministic Turing machine (M), that when processed, the time taken to resolve it should not take more than $p|x|$ time, where the input is (x, y) . In case the input is x , then there should be a string y in the same language so that $M(x, y) = 1$, otherwise, if the x does not belong to the language and all strings y of length $q|x|$, $M(x, y) = 0$. The most famous problem that belongs to this category is the travelling salesman problem. Before we move on to the next category is worth mentioning that this category is split to NP-complete and NP-hard problems. These two subcategories, along with the P class being a subset of NP, need to be analyzed further and it shall be done so at a later stage.

ZPP, or Zero-error Probabilistic Polynomial time class contains the problems that a probabilistic Turing machine will always give the correct answer. These answers are either YES or NO, they are always correct, and the calculation time is of polynomial complexity. A second Turing machine with probable outcomes YES, NO, or DON'T KNOW is also considered to be equivalent and returns DON'T KNOW in 50% of the cases (with the rest being the correct response).

The Randomized Polynomial time class is the one that is based (like the ZPP) on a probabilistic Turing machine and it has the properties of running always on polynomial time, if the answer is YES then it always returns YES, and finally, if the answer is NO, then it returns NO with a probability of 50% (else

it will return YES). It is worth noting that class P is a subset of RP, which is a subset in its turn, of class NP. However, we do not know whether these restrictions are strict and more so, the problem that P is equal to RP, instead of just a subset, remains unsolved in computer science. A similar class to RP also exists, namely co-RP with the main difference being that NO is always right while YES might be wrong. This means that it can accept all YES instances, but it might reject the NO instances. The following class that we will examine, can give us an error on both YES and NO instances, thusly containing both RP and co-RP. The intersection of RP and co-RP is the actual definition of ZPP class.

The penultimate class is the Bounded-error Probabilistic Polynomial time class where we use a probabilistic Turing machine (again like ZPP and RP) but in this case, the machine has an error probability of producing the correct result standing at 1/3 of all instances. For a problem to belong to this class, its algorithm should be allowed to flip a coin in order to make a random decision, to always run in polynomial time, and on any given run of the algorithm there is a 1/3 probability of producing an error, even if the results are only YES or NO. Formally, if we have a language and a probabilistic Turing machine then the machine should run in a polynomial time on all inputs, for all inputs belonging to the language the output is 1 with a probability greater than or equal to 2/3, and for any input not belonging to the language the answer should be 1 again, with a probability less than or equal to 1/3. The problem of the polynomial identity testing (determining whether a polynomial is identically equal to the zero polynomial, when you have access to the value of the polynomial for any given input, but not to the coefficients of it) is famously part of this class. The problem of P being equal to BPP is also unsolved in computer science.

The final class is the Bounded-error Quantum Polynomial time (BQP) class where the problems that lie here are solvable by a quantum computer in polynomial time with a probability error of 1/3 at most for all instances. This class is the quantum analogue of the BPP class and utilizes quantum computers that we described earlier. This class is also the one with the most interesting problems as humanity is heading forward in technology. The most famous examples that belong to this category are the factorization of an integer into prime numbers (also known as Shor's algorithm), the discrete logarithm (where a solution to the base of the algorithm and the result produced is calculated), the simulation of quantum systems (where a Turing machine can simulate quantum phenomena without slowing down as proposed by Yuri Manin and Richard Feynman) and the approximation of Jones polynomial at certain roots of unit (this is also known as the knot polynomial where an oriented knot is assigned the Laurent polynomial in the variable of $t^{1/2}$ with integer coefficients).

As a side note here, it should be mentioned that the classes NP, RP and ZPP all have witnesses albeit they do not all need them. When trying to prove that a language and a Turing machine can produce the desired output, the following verification is used:

As an example, consider a verifier V for a set X is a Turing machine such that:

If x is in X then there exists a string w such that V(x,w) accepts (TRUE);

If x is not in X, then for all strings w, V(x,w) rejects (FALSE).

The string w can be thought of as the proof of membership, i.e., that x is a member of the X set. In the case of short proofs (of length bounded by a polynomial in the size of the input) which can be efficiently verified (V is a polynomial-time deterministic Turing machine), the string w is called a witness.

The image below shows how the various complexity classes are interrelated and the common sets or subsets:

By MarioS - Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=25006447>

The next classification that will be examined is the super-polynomial time. In this case, an algorithm that is not bounded above by any polynomial, is said to run in super-polynomial time. This time complexity class is symbolized with $\omega(n^c)$, where c represents all constants and n is the number of bits in the input. Algorithms that belong to this class are not practical and usually are unsolvable.

While some algorithms can be solved in polynomial time and others in exponential time, there is a set of problems that can be solved in a time frame bigger than that of a polynomial time but smaller than exponential time. This class of problems is said to be solved in quasi polynomial time and they come from their reduction from the NP class to another one. A good example of this type of problems is the 3SAT problem. The 3SAT problem, or Boolean Satisfiability Problem examines the case where, given a Boolean formula, the replacement of all its variables with the values TRUE or FALSE can always result to TRUE. While the problem has been the first one to be proven to be an NP complete problem, there is no known algorithm that efficiently solves all the SAT problems, and it is generally believed that there is not one. This hypothesis remains unsolved in mathematics and its solution is equivalent to the P versus NP problem that will be discussed later. Despite that, SAT algorithms have been used in artificial intelligence and circuit design that involve tens of thousands of variables and formulas consisting of millions of symbols. Another example of this class of problems is the Steiner tree problem.

The image below showcases the minimum Steiner trees of vertices of regular polygons with $N = 3$ to 8 sides. The lowest network length L for $N > 5$, is the circumference less one side. Squares represent Steiner points.

By Cmglee - Own work, CC BY-SA 4.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=83330247>

There is a classification of problems that the time needed to conclude is less than the exponential time complexity but significantly higher than that of a polynomial time. This class of problems are said to be solved in a sub-exponential time and they are somewhat more tractable than those of exponential time. However, there is no clear definition of this classification of problems. The most accepted definition states that a problem can be considered as belonging to this class if it can be solved in running times (given any input, that is) that the logarithms grow smaller than any given polynomial. There are a few dependencies on the definition of this algorithm that will not be mentioned but suffices to say that several of the parameters involved could contain algorithms of their own that need to be calculated in order for the problem to run. This classification could contain the problem of the integer factorization as well as the general number field sieve. Both problems have algorithms that can be solved in $2^{o(n)}$ time, where n is the number of inputs.

The exponential class on the other hand, consists of problem that their time frame is upper bounded by $2^{\text{poly}(n)}$, where $\text{poly}(n)$ is some polynomial in n , or more formally, the exponent is raised to the k (so n^k) where k is a constant. Between the two classes of sub-exponential and exponential time, lies an unproven hypothesis, known as the exponential time hypothesis. This is an unproven computational hardness assumption that states that some, not all, NP-complete problems cannot be solved in sub-exponential time in the worst case. This will imply that $P \neq NP$, which delves in the known problem of P vs NP that will be discussed later.

The next classification of algorithms is a favourite of mine! However impossible, there is a classification of problems that runs in factorial time. As you know, the factorial of a number is the product of all previous numbers leading up to the given number and is symbolized by the exclamation mark (!). So, for example, $4!$ is the result of $1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 4$ which is 24. The most famous problem that showcases this kind of time complexity is bogosort. Bogosort is a sorting algorithm that is based on trial and error. Basically, given an array of n integers in an unsorted manner, bogosort will shuffle the list repeatedly until

the resulting array is sorted. This algorithm is also known as stupid sort, slowsort, derp sort (from the derp meme) or monkey sort (sharing patrimony with the infinite monkeys' problem, where if you put an infinite number of monkeys with each one given a typewriter, then it is definite that one monkey will write the complete works of Shakespeare). In the spirit of stupid algorithms, there is also the bozosort (from the infamous clown Bozo, I guess) that will take random numbers and input them in a list and if the list is not sorted, it will choose randomly two elements from the list and swap them. Then it will check again and repeat the previous step. But wait! There is more! Bogobogosort is an algorithm that was designed not to succeed before the heat death of the universe given any sizable list. It works by recursively calling itself with smaller and smaller copies of the original list to see if they are sorted. The base case is a single element, which is always sorted. For other cases, it compares the last element to the maximum element from the previous elements in the list. If the last element is greater or equal, it checks if the order of the copy matches the previous version, and if so returns. Otherwise, it rearranges the current copy of the list and restarts its recursive check. But this is nothing compared to my all-time favourite sorting algorithm from this class. Introducing the quantum bogosort, a hypothetical sorting algorithm based on bogosort which was created as an inside joke among computer scientists. The algorithm generates a random list of integers for its input, checks if the list is sorted, and, if it is not, destroys the universe. Yes, you read that correctly! It destroys the universe. Assuming that the many-worlds interpretation is true (infinite parallel universes), the use of this algorithm will result in the existence of exactly one surviving universe where the input is successfully sorted. The many worlds interpretation can be used to explain the Schrödinger's cat experiment, as it is illustrated below:

By Christian Schirm - Own work, CC0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=17512691>

The final classification for the time complexity classes of problems is the double exponential time class. For a problem to belong to this class, it must have an upper bound in time of $2^{2^{\text{poly}(n)}}$, where $\text{poly}(n)$ is some polynomial in n . There are three well known problems that belong to this class. The first one is the decision procedures for Presburger arithmetic which is the first-order theory of natural numbers consisting of 0 and 1 and the addition symbol (+) and the equality sign. As a side note, a first-order language, or first-order logic, is the principle where we use quantifiable variables over non-logical objects, and it is the standard for the formalization of mathematics into axioms. A good example would be "Kyriakos is a man", which by the first-order logic we get "there exists x such that x is Kyriakos and x is a man". So, the procedure to decide whether an input fulfils the Presburger arithmetic lies in the double exponential time class. The second problem is computing the Gröbner basis for the worst-case scenario. The Gröbner basis is a particular kind of generating set of an ideal in a polynomial ring $K[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ over a field K . In mathematics, there is a field called abstract algebra. Abstract algebra is the study of algebraic

structures like rings, vector spaces, lattices, groups, and fields. A simple enough explanation is that all the permutations (combinations) that occur when you spin a Rubik's cube are called a group.

My own photo of my Rubik's cube!

A ring is the study of algebraic structures in which the addition and multiplication are defined and have similar properties to the operations as those are defined for integers. However, the numbers used can also be complex (i.e., have an imaginary part), polynomials, square matrices, power series, or functions. The ring itself, in mathematics, is defined as an abelian group with the previously mentioned operations, where the multiplication operation is associative, and distributive over the addition operation having additionally an identity element (this is an element that leaves any element combined with it unchanged). Just to see everything coming around, here is the definition of the abelian group. An abelian group is a group in which the results of applying the group operation to two group elements does not depend on the order in which the elements are written. This leads to the ideal. The ideal is a special subset of a ring, such as the even numbers. In this case, any even number added to another even number preserves the "even" concept and any number multiplied by an even is still an even. So, the algorithm that can create a generating set of an ideal in a polynomial (this is the Gröbner basis), for the worst-case scenario of producing such a set, belongs to the double exponential time classification. Speaking of rings, if the multiplication commutative clause from them is dropped, this leads to division rings. Some of the division rings are finite dimensional \mathbb{R} -vector spaces and those specific ones are even numbered. There is not an odd-dimensional division algebra. This is known due to the hairy ball theorem, which states that a hairy ball cannot be combed! This goes to show that computer science is not the only science that has a sense of humor. For your viewing pleasure, here is the aforementioned ball that cannot be combed:

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The third problem that dominates this classification is the quantifier elimination on real closed fields. In mathematics, the real closed field is defined to be the field (set on which the normal operations of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division are defined and behave as they would on rational or real numbers; a what is also known as fundamental algebraic structure), that has the same first-order properties as the field of real numbers. The quantifier elimination is defined as the concept of simplification used in mathematical logic and theoretical computer science. This simplification on a set of real numbers with the properties mentioned above requires an algorithm that runs in double exponential time.

With all that said and done, how is time complexity calculated for any given algorithm? To find the complexity of an algorithm the number of machine instructions will be executed as a function of the size of the input needs to be known, and then simplify the expression to the largest term, including simplifying any constant factor. As an example, a program executes $2N + 2$ instructions. The complexity of this algorithm is $O(n)$. As n rises (the input gets larger), the second term becomes insignificantly small. If n is in the order of a billion, then 2 is insignificant. It will not make an actual difference to the result. Since our input is in the order of billions, it does not matter if it is one billion, two billion or three billion. The order of magnitude is still the same. Thus, the initial 2 is dropped and the complexity becomes $O(n)$. In general, a one – time pass is considered linear (one dimension, single for loop), a two-dimensional pass (such as nested for loops) is considered quadratic ($n*n$, which is n^2), and a working area divided in half with each iteration (such as quick sort) will be logarithmic. In conclusion, what is of interest here is the rate of growth of time with respect to the amount of inputs taken during the algorithm execution.

As mentioned before, the complexity taken into consideration here is the big O notation, which denotes the worst-case scenario. The best-case scenario (or lower bound) is the big omega notation (Ω) whilst if the upper and lower bound are taken into consideration together (this is known as the tight bound) we get the big theta notation (Θ). Their graphical representation can be seen in the graphs below where the following is assumed:

For a given function $g(n)$ it is denoted that:

$$O(g(n)) = \{f(n) \text{ there exists positive constants } c \text{ and } n_0 \text{ such that } 0 \leq f(n) \leq c * g(n)\}$$

$$\Omega(g(n)) = \{f(n) \text{ there exists positive constants } c \text{ and } n_0 \text{ such that } 0 \leq c * g(n) \leq f(n)\}$$

$$\Theta(g(n)) = \{f(n) \text{ there exists positive constants } c_1, c_2 \text{ and } n_0 \text{ such that } 0 \leq c_1 * g(n) \leq f(n) \leq c_2 * g(n)\}$$

For all $n > n_0$

<https://www.hackerearth.com/practice/basic-programming/complexity-analysis/time-and-space-complexity/tutorial/>

To clear things up a bit more, there is another detail that needs to be mentioned here. The way the classification of any algorithm into any category is measured, is using DTIME. DTIME is the computational resource of computation time for a deterministic Turing machine. It represents the amount of time (or number of computation steps) that a physical computer would take in order to solve a computational problem using a specific algorithm. The definition for P class is given below as an example using the DTIME computational resource:

$$P = \bigcup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \text{DTIME}(n^k)$$

In case of using a nondeterministic Turing machine, then the computation time is measured in NTIME. NTIME belongs to a category where there are a lot of generalizations and restrictions. A lot of research needs to take place in what determines computational time in nondeterministic Turing machines, as the comparison of DTIME and other computational resources is not very clear. We do know though that the time complexity using a deterministic Turing machine for an algorithm that is $O(n)$ is not the same as the time complexity yielding from a nondeterministic Turing machine for the same function.

$$\text{DTIME}(O(n)) \neq \text{NTIME}(O(n))$$

There is a special case of time resources that uses an alternating Turing machine; a nondeterministic Turing machine that has states which are divided into existential and universal states (existential is considered a state where some of the transitions lead to an accepting state, while a universal state accepts inputs where all the transitions lead to an accepting state). This resource is called ATIME. The classification that is used in such a Turing machine is alternating between classes NP and co-NP (for a decision problem to belong in co-NP, precisely if for any no-instance x there is a "certificate" which a polynomial-time algorithm can use to verify that x is a no-instance). As expected, whether $\text{NP} = \text{co-NP}$ or $\text{NP} \neq \text{co-NP}$ is also an open problem in computer science.

Before looking into space complexity, the properties of the complexity classes should be viewed. These properties are applicable to both time and space complexity and they are as follows: the closure of a complexity class, its hardness, and its completeness. A class is said to be closed under a certain operation when said operation when applied to one of the members of the set always produces a member of the same set. A great example is a set containing only zeros. This set is closed to addition, subtraction, and multiplication as any of the above as $0 - 0$, $0 * 0$ and $0 + 0$ always results to 0. The closure property is one of the ways that classes can be separated as if a class is closed under subtraction while another similar one is not, this means that they are two different classes. Another way to define classes would be through the concept of reduction which will lead to the next two properties. A reduction is a transformation

of one problem to another. It basically states that if a difficult problem can be changed to be in another form, then the second problem that occurs would be at least as difficult as the first one. In case the second problem can be solved under an algorithm, then this means that the initial problem can be reduced to the second problem. There are a lot of methods for reduction as stated earlier, along with Cook reduction (if problem A can be reduced to problem B and B is a decision problem that can be solved using a routine, then A can be solved if given the subroutine for B), polynomial-time reduction (where a problem is solved using another problem which is solved by a subroutine and thus if the first problem's inputs can be transformed or reduced to the second problem's inputs, then it can be solved by calling the subroutine one or multiple times; if the time taken to transform the problem and the number the subroutine is called is polynomial, then the first problem is polynomial-time reducible), and the log-space reduction (a deterministic Turing machine can keep a constant number of pointers into the input along with logarithmic fixed size integers; this machine has polynomially-many configurations and thus log-space reductions are actually polynomial time reductions). This notion of reduction enables us to reduce problems in a class to hard. This means that if every problem in a class can be reduced to an original problem, and that problem is solvable, then the class is labelled as hard since every problem included in the class is as hard as the original that have been reduced to. A great example are the problems that are included in the NP-hard class. If a problem is in a class and it is hard for said class, then the problem is complete for the class. This means that the NP-complete class contains the most difficult problems in NP class, in the sense that these are the most likely not to be a part of the P class. Despite the many theories and efforts, the unsolved problem of whether $P = NP$ or $P \neq NP$.

An open problem in computer science, P vs NP puts two of the biggest classes in computational theory as opponents. The problem is to determine whether every language accepted by some nondeterministic algorithm in polynomial time is also accepted by some deterministic algorithm in polynomial time. In other words, it asks whether every problem whose solution can be quickly verified can also be solved quickly (meaning finding a solution in polynomial time). The problem is one of the seven Millennium Prize Problems as selected by the Clay Mathematics Institute and carries a \$1,000,000 prize for the person who will provide the first correct solution. The answer to this question would determine whether problems that can be verified in polynomial time can also be solved in polynomial time. If the answer turns out to be that $P \neq NP$, which has long been suspected, this would mean that there are problems that belong in the NP class that can be verified easier than be solved in polynomial time. The significance of this problem and why the reward is so high, is due to the fact that any solution to this problem would impact mathematics, cryptography, artificial intelligence, game theory, philosophy, economics, and many, many more. If $P = NP$, then this means that cryptography algorithms will collapse as they belong to the NP class, and simply put, no more security (among other things); thus no more secure payments online, no more HTTPS, and no more Internet. While there are several problems that are NP-complete (meaning they can be reduced in smaller problems able to be solved in polynomial time, thus verifying the bigger problem in polynomial time as a result) this does not mean that all NP problems can be reduced to NP-complete problems. A NP-complete problem is at least as tough to be resolved as any other problem in NP. For example, the Boolean satisfiability problem is NP-complete due to the Cook–Levin theorem that is NP-complete. Despite this, there are several problems that have been proven to be NP-complete, yet there is no fast algorithm for them to be solved in polynomial time. As a side note, there are several problems that are NP-hard, which means that are at least as hard as NP problems (all NP problems can be reduced in polynomial time to them). Euler describes the above in the diagram below:

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A lot of complexity classes are defined by the interactive proof system. This works by setting an abstract machine that models computation as the exchange of messages between the prover P and verifier V . While the prover has unlimited computational power, the verifier has bounded computational power. Due to the prover being untrustworthy though (this will prevent all languages from being trivially recognized by the proof system by having the prover solve for each string whether it belongs in a language or not), the verifier must conduct an interrogation of the prover by asking successive rounds of question and will be accepted as trustworthy if a high degree of confidence is developed that the string belongs to said language. This concept is used to generalize the definition of the NP class and offers an insight into cryptography and approximation algorithms. Problems that are solved using an interactive proof system belong to a class called Interactive Polynomial time, or IP, while problems that allow the usage of quantum computation on an interactive proof system belong to a class called Quantum Interactive Polynomial time, or QIP.

While most of the problems included in the classes mentioned above are decision problems (YES or NO), there are also classes that describe other kind of problems like counting problems, function problems (which were mentioned earlier), and promise problems. Counting problems ask how many solutions there are to a problem and is symbolized with the notation $\#P$ (pronounced sharp P). $\#P$ problems can be thought as the counting version of the NP complexity class. Promise problems are decision problems that the machines operating them as well as the algorithms ruling them have been promised that the input they will receive belongs to the language in question. These inputs may result to a YES or NO answer but since the algorithm was promised something belonging to the language, then the output is open, and in cases, the algorithm may never reach a conclusion (halt).

While time complexity takes the lion's share of the complexity theory, space complexity also needs to be investigated to get a clear picture of the problems at hand. Space complexity is the hardware needed for such a feat, usually meaning the amount of memory needed to execute a program and produce output. We define it as the metric of the storage in memory needed by the algorithm in relation to its inputs and it is also represented by the big O notation. So, the space in memory is utilized for storing the programs' instructions, the constant values, the variable values, and the function calls, jump statements, etc. This amount of memory is divided into three sections, the instruction space, the environmental stack, and the data space. The total amount of memory needed is defined as the input space (all the variables mentioned before and instructions) and the auxiliary space (the part of the memory needed for the program to run; a temporary space used by the algorithm during execution).

The most important reason needed to calculate space complexity is that some algorithms are designed with particular limitations, like an upper bound on total storage. A miscalculation of the space

complexity can lead to imprecise and rough results. Using deterministic and non-deterministic Turing machines (as explained above), the complexity classes for space complexity can be derived using a set of languages and the respective Turing machine.

To calculate the space complexity needed by the algorithm, the following two parts are taken into consideration. A fixed part that is defined as the space required to store data and variables that are independent of the size of the problem, and a variable part where the space is determined by the variables whose size is dependent on the size of the problem (for example, dynamic memory allocation). As space complexity $S(p)$ of an algorithm p is defined as:

$$S(p) = A + Sp(I)$$

Where A is the fixed part and $S(I)$ is the variable part of the algorithm which depends on instance characteristic I .

The definition of space complexity hides a very interesting tidbit regarding the amount of resources needed to solve problems that are considered difficult to solve: Let M be a deterministic Turing Machine (TM) that halts on all inputs. The space complexity of M is the function:

$$f : N \rightarrow N$$

where, $f(n)$ is the maximum number of cells of tape and M scans any input of length M . If the space complexity of M is $f(n)$, we can state that M runs in space $f(n)$. If the space complexity of M is $f(n)$ we can say that M runs in space $f(n)$. By this, we can estimate the space complexity of the Turing Machine using asymptotic notation. For this, we consider the following to be a function:

$$f : N \rightarrow R^+$$

The above definition will allow us to define the space complexity as follows:

$$DSPACE = \{L \mid L \text{ is a language decided by an } O(f(n)) \text{ space deterministic TM}\}$$

$$NSPACE = \{L \mid L \text{ is a language decided by an } O(f(n)) \text{ space non-deterministic TM}\}$$

PSPACE is the class of languages that are decidable in polynomial space on a deterministic Turing machine while NPSPACE is the class of languages that are decidable in non-polynomial space on a deterministic Turing machine. Notice here that there is no reference to a nondeterministic Turing machine at all. This is due to Savitch's theorem that states that if a nondeterministic Turing machine can solve a problem using $f(n)$ space, then an ordinary deterministic Turing machine can solve the same problem in the square of that space bound. This means that despite the fact that nondeterminism can produce exponential gains in time complexity, in space complexity it makes no difference at all. Savitch's theorem, as proven by Walter Savitch in 1970, states that for any function:

$$f \in \Omega(\log(n)), \quad \text{then} \quad NSPACE(f(n)) \subseteq DSPACE((f(n))^2)$$

A direct aftermath of the theorem as well as the fact that the square of a polynomial function is still a polynomial, we get that problems that belong in the P classification of problems and problems that belong to the NP classification of problems, have the same space complexity, i.e.

$$PSPACE = NPSPACE$$

This is, at best, a bizarre result, because earlier on it was mentioned that the problems that belong in P class and those belonging to NP class have different time complexities, and the problem between the P and NP time complexities is an open problem in computer science. It seems that in the case of space complexity though, $P = NP$.

In relation to DSPACE and NSPACE, the two main complexity classes of space complexity, PSPACE and NPSPACE, can be defined as follows:

$$\text{PSPACE} = \bigcup_{c \in \mathbb{Z}^+} \text{DSPACE}(n^c)$$

And

$$\text{NPSPACE} = \bigcup_{c \in \mathbb{Z}^+} \text{NSPACE}(n^c)$$

Space complexity introduces the space hierarchy theorem that states that, for all space – constructible functions $f(n)$, there is a problem that can be solved by a machine with $f(n)$ memory space but cannot be solved by a machine with asymptotically less than $f(n)$ space. The containments between complexity classes are as follows:

$$\text{DTIME}(f(n)) \subseteq \text{DSPACE}(f(n)) \subseteq \text{NSPACE}(f(n)) \subseteq \text{DTIME}(2^{O(f(n))})$$

Furthermore, the Immerman–Szelepcsényi theorem states that for a function f such that:

$$f \in \Omega(\log(n))$$

Then $\text{NSPACE}(f(n))$ is closed under complementation. This means that $\text{NSPACE}(f(n))$ does not accept any operation that might determine the complement of the mathematical set. The theorem in its general form states that $\text{NSPACE}(s(n)) = \text{co-NSPACE}(s(n))$ for any function $s(n) \geq \log n$; this is also stated equivalently as $\text{NL} = \text{co-NL}$. The proof for this theorem gave the Gödel prize to Immerman and Szelepcsényi in 1995 and has solved another problem called the second LBA problem (the problem states that for any Linear Bounded Automaton – a restricted form of Turing machine – is $\text{NSPACE}(O(n)) = \text{co-SPACE}(O(n))$ with the answer to this being yes). In its simplest form, the theorem states that if a non-deterministic machine can solve a problem, then another machine with the same amount of resources and bounds can solve its complement problem (i.e. giving the answer yes in place of no and vice versa) in the same asymptotic amount of space. This is the weird thing that was mentioned earlier, were the same conjecture does not apply for time complexity.

Generally speaking, there are only two space complexity classes. These are the L and the NL. The L space complexity class is the class of decision problems that can be solved by a deterministic Turing machine using a logarithmic amount of writable memory. The logarithmic space assigned to the problem sufficiently holds a constant number of pointers into the input and a logarithmic number of Boolean flags, due to basic logarithmic space algorithms utilizing the memory in this way. Logarithmic space or logspace has as a main function storing a polynomial-magnitude number in logspace and use it to remember pointer to a position of the input. This has been proven useful when the input is actually too big to fit in the RAM of a computer, such as long DNA sequences and databases.

The NL space complexity class (Non-deterministic Logarithmic-space class) is the class of decision problems that can be solved by a non-deterministic Turing machine using a logarithmic amount of memory space. While a deterministic Turing machine is also a non-deterministic Turing machine, we can write that L is a subset of NL. However, as with P and NP, the relationships $L = \text{NL}$, $L = P$, and $L = \text{NP}$ are unsolved problems in computer science. One of the many problems that are part of the NL-complete class is the ST satisfiability problem, where S and T are the nodes in a directed graph and asks the questions whether T is reachable from S. NL is simply described as containing precisely those languages that are expressible in first – order logic with an additional transitive closure operator.

Several smaller subclasses exist in space complexity, the most important of which are FL and NC. FL is the set of function problems that can be solved by a deterministic Turing machine in a logarithmic amount of memory space. NC contains the set of decision problems that are decidable in

polylogarithmic time on a parallel computer with a polynomial number of processors. Basically, it states that a problem belongs in NC if there are constants c and k that the solution provided for the problem is in time $O(\log^c n)$ using $O(n^k)$ parallel processors. This set of problems can be solved efficiently on a parallel computer. Problems in this class include matrix multiplication, integer addition, multiplication, and division. The class AC belongs to the circuit complexity theory that is closely linked to space complexity. Each subclass (AC^i) consists of the languages recognized by Boolean circuits with a depth of $O(\log^i n)$ and a polynomial number of unlimited fan-in AND and OR gates. Circuit complexity is a branch of computational complexity theory, where Boolean functions are classified according to the size or depth of the Boolean circuits that compute them. The diagram below shows a simple Boolean circuit where \wedge nodes are the AND gates, \vee are the OR gates and \neg are the NOT gates.

By Jaydavidmartin - Created in Latex with TikZ package, CC BY-SA 4.0, <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?curid=63595879>

Boolean circuits are the best examples when it comes to determine non-uniform models of computation, where inputs of different lengths are processed by different circuits. This is in contrast with uniform Turing machines where the same computational device is used for all possible lengths. The uniform descriptions of the Boolean circuits are polynomial-time (where a deterministic Turing machine M runs in polynomial time and for all n in \mathbb{N} , M outputs a description of C_n on input 1^n) and logspace (where a deterministic Turing machine M runs in logarithmic time and for all n in \mathbb{N} , M outputs a description of C_n on input 1^n). As an example, when a certain language A belongs to the time-complexity $\text{TIME}(t(n))$ for some function $t: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, then A has a circuit complexity of $O(t^2(n))$. The relationship between the various space time complexity classes can be summarized as follows:

$$NC^1 \subseteq L \subseteq NL \subseteq AC^1 \subseteq NC^2 \subseteq P$$

The two most important classes for computational complexity, time, and space, are related with the following statement:

$$NL \subseteq P \subseteq NP \subseteq PSPACE \subseteq EXPTIME \subseteq EXPSPACE$$

Where \subseteq denotes that the previous class is a subset of the next one.

The graph below summarizes the classes of problems that are considered in complexity theory as well as the relationship between them. If a class is a strict subset of another class, then the line is solid, if it is unknown then the line is dotted.

Graph is from the Wikipedia page for Complexity Class, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Complexity_class

At the beginning of this study, a quote by Edsger Wybe Dijkstra was used to introduce the concept of complexity. Dijkstra also proposed the shortest path algorithm that now bears his name in his honour. Dijkstra's algorithm, or the shortest path algorithm, proposed in 1956 and published in a paper by him in 1959, is an algorithm for finding the shortest paths between nodes in a weighted graph. While graphs are a big part of complexity and computer science, they are out of the scope of this study. It is sufficient to note that they may represent road networks that connect cities, metro networks, etc. each road or line (or edge as it is formally known) having a cost in order to traverse it. The algorithm has many applications in everyday life such as powerline mappings, and oil pipelines. The algorithm, given the starting node (in the case of a road map, the starting city) will calculate all the shortest paths to all the other nodes. The complexity for the algorithm is $\Theta(|E| \cdot T_{dk} + |V| \cdot T_{em})$, where T_{dk} , and T_{em} are the complexities of the decrease-key and extract-minimum operations, while E and V are the number of edges and the numbers of vertices in a given graph. An improvement to this algorithm is A^* . A^* is also a

graph traversal and path search algorithm which uses heuristics to guide its search. This algorithm is preferred in a lot of fields of computer science due to its completeness, optimality, optimal efficiency, and that it considers the cost/distance already travelled into account when calculating the shortest paths. This algorithm's drawback however is that its space complexity is exponential as it stores the generated nodes in memory. A* is often used in common pathfinding problems in video games but it was originally designed as general graph traversal algorithm for a robot called Shakey, as a part of its artificial intelligence.

Despite relying on time and hardware to indicate complexity, the algorithmic information theory that studies the relationship between computation and information of computably generated objects, has shown that computation incompressibility mimics the relations found in information theory. Essentially, algorithmic information theory principally studies complexity measures on strings or other data structures and declares that the information contained in a string is equivalent to the length of the most-compressed possible self-contained representation of that string. By this definition, a 4000-page book contains less information than 4000 pages with completely random letters on them. This is what is known as entropy in information theory. As a side note here, information theory is the study of quantification, storage, and communication of information. It is one of the most important subjects in computer science, and its applications can be seen through the achievements of the Voyager missions, the realization of mobile phones, the development of the internet, cryptography, quantum computing, thermal physics, intelligence gathering, black holes, and many more. Entropy is the average level of information, surprise, or uncertainty inherent in the variable's possible outcome. For example, the traditional coin toss has 1 bit of entropy with a surprise factor of 1/2, given that no other outcome is possible other than heads or tails. If the coin is rigged and it will always land on heads for example, then the surprise is 0 and the entropy of the coin toss will be 0 bits.

THROUGH 20 YEARS OF EFFORT, WE'VE SUCCESSFULLY TRAINED EVERYONE TO USE PASSWORDS THAT ARE HARD FOR HUMANS TO REMEMBER, BUT EASY FOR COMPUTERS TO GUESS.

The strings mentioned in algorithmic information theory are random and are dependent on the Turing machine used to define their complexity, as any choice of string will give us identical asymptotic results and any string chosen is invariant up to an additive constant, relying only on the choice of the universal Turing machine. The complexity that occurs through this process is called Kolmogorov complexity and states that the complexity of an object (such as a piece of text) is the length of the shortest computer program in a predetermined computer language that produces the object as its output. Kolmogorov complexity is used to prove impossibility results such as Turing's halting problem. Interestingly, there is no program that computes a lower bound for Kolmogorov complexity for each text that can return a value greater than the length of the program itself. In this case, for each string (which is considered a program), the smallest output will be the string itself. Hence, no single program can compute the exact Kolmogorov complexity for infinitely many texts.

Through information theory there is also another type of complexity worth mentioning, that deals with the information that is fed through a dynamic system. This discovery in 1993 by Bates and Shepard introduced the information fluctuation complexity. Information fluctuation complexity is a quantity defined within information theory and is outlined as the fluctuation of information about entropy, and it is derived from the fluctuations in the predominance of order and chaos in a dynamic system. Any complex dynamic system will evolve in time as it receives information (be that stable or unstable), it exhibits alternating information gain and loss. This fluctuation of information the dynamic system receives puts it in an equivalent state of remembering and forgetting, which is an essential of non-trivial computation. The information gained by the system because of this fluctuation of information on multiple states, can be proven to depend only on the increase in state information from the initial to the final state. This proof is applicable to any probability distribution and has been used over the years in many fields such as complexity theory, chaotic dynamics, air traffic control, and many others.

It should be mentioned that there are some problems for which the algorithm is known and can be theoretically solved, but practically solving them will take too many resources, both in time and space. Problems with their respective algorithms that belong to this category are called intractable problems.

Lastly, on the 21st of March 2021, when this paper has been completed, there was a great discovery reported where an extra solution for the sum of three cubes problem for number 3 was discovered. The same problem but for the famous Douglas Adams number of 42, was discovered the previous September. Scientists are looking for solutions to the problem shown by the equation below, also known as the sum of three cubes:

$$x^3 + y^3 + z^3 = k$$

where x , y , z , and k are integers. The general form of this equation is still unproven in Mathematics as it takes a lot of processing power to be resolved. However, in September 2019, the professors at the University of Bristol and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) managed to solve the $k = 42$ problem by harnessing the processing power of 500,000 home computers, thus creating a crowd-sourced platform made from processing capacity otherwise not used. This equation is a type of Diophantine Equation. The reason this is brought up is because Diophantine Equations are fascinating when it comes to complexity. When they are in their linear form ($ax + by + c = 0$) are solvable in polynomial time. When they are in their quadratic form ($ax^2 + by = c$) they belong to the NP-complete class, while at the same time, some of them have polynomial-time solutions. They do not belong to the NP classification though as determining whether Diophantine equations have solutions is undecidable, and every problem in NP class is decidable. Once the Diophantine is in its cubed form or higher, they are undecidable.

Sometimes things are not that simple. Sometimes problems are complicated. And though we try to make them easier and less complicated, sometimes complexity and complex go hand in hand. This does not mean that we do not have to try and make it simple. It is only befitting to close this study with another quote from the scientist that with one of his quotes this study opened. On complexity and

simplicity Dijkstra said, "Simplicity is a great virtue, but it requires hard work to achieve it and education to appreciate it. And to make matters worse: complexity sells better". Both in computer engineering, and in life...

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